

Structure of Heptazolidine

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Details of the structure of heptazolidine, a carbazole alkaloid isolated from *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. and Arn. is reported.

In connection with our work on carbazole alkaloids on taxonomic considerations, we undertook the examination of *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. and Arn. (Fam.: Rutaceae, Sub. Fam.: Aurantoidae, Subtribe: Clausinae) from which we reported the structure of heptazoline¹ (1). The structure of heptazoline has been confirmed by the synthesis of cyclophetazoline¹ and its total synthesis by Sharma and Kapil². Previously we reported³ the structure of heptazolidine (2), another alkaloid of *C. heptaphylla*. Now we report the details of the structure of heptazolidine.

Heptazolidine, C₁₈H₁₉NO₃ (2) (M⁺ 293), an optically inactive homogeneous compound, showed the colour change from deep red to green with concentrated H₂SO₄. The analytical data showed the presence of one methoxyl and one C-Me groups. The ir spectrum of the compound showed the presence of one NH group (3400), unsaturation (1650), aromatic nucleus (1510, 1315, 985 and 965), aromatic C-Me (1380) and aromatic ether (1270 and 1190 cm⁻¹). All these data suggest that 2 is a carbazole derivative. The uv absorption spectrum of the compound was very similar to those of pyranocarbazoles¹. The pmr spectrum showed the presence of one NH proton (δ 8.1), one aromatic proton singlet at δ 7.5 and a meta-coupled proton at δ 7.67, two ortho-coupled aromatic protons at δ 6.94 and 7.18 (J 8.5 Hz each), two pairs of one-proton doublets at δ 6.63 and 5.65 (J 10 Hz each), two three-proton singlets for one C-methyl and one aromatic methoxyl at δ 2.3 and 3.98, respectively, a six-proton singlet at δ 1.49 for a gem-dimethyl group. The sharp singlet at δ 1.49 together with the two proton doublets at δ 6.63 and 5.65 confirm the presence of a 2,2-dimethyl-Δ⁸-pyran ring in 2. The aromatic proton singlet at δ 7.9 for H-4 is shielded showing that the methoxyl group is at 3-position. The proton at δ 7.67 was attributed to H-5. The mass spectrum shows the molecular ion peak at m/z 293. With a loss of 15 mass units, it shows the high intensity peak for a substituted carbazolopyrillium ion (3) like those of girinimbine and mahanimbine. This confirms the 2,2-dimethyl-Δ⁸-pyranocarbazole skeleton of heptazolidine.

On hydrogenation heptazolidine furnished dihydroheptazolidine (4), C₁₉H₂₁NO₃ (M⁺ 295),

m.p. 180°. The uv spectrum of 4 was distinctly different from 2,6-dimethoxy-3-methylcarbazole, glycozolidine (5) and dihydrogrinimbine (6). The substitution pattern as revealed from the pmr spectra suggest that probably the methoxyl group is at 3 and aromatic methyl group is at 6 positions. This was also supported by the nonidentity of heptazolidine with koenimbine (7).

The point of fusion of 2,2-dimethyl-Δ⁸-pyran system with an aromatic system, like those in many coumarins and alkaloids has been deduced from ozonolysis experiments⁴⁻⁷. In consideration of the isolation⁸ of 1-formyl-2-hydroxy-3-methyl carbazole (9) from girinimbine (10) and mahanimbine (11), we subjected heptazolidine to ozonolysis to have further proof for the fusion of the 2,2-dimethyl-Δ⁸-pyran ring with the carbazole skeleton. Heptazolidine on ozonisation furnished (i) a phenolic aldehyde, (ii) a neutral product and (iii) acetone from volatile fraction.

The phenolic aldehyde, C₁₈H₁₇NO₃ (M⁺ 255), m.p. 110°, showed the presence of chelated NH,

OH, chelated aromatic aldehyde and aromatic system from its ir spectrum. The uv absorption spectrum of the compound showed it to be a 1-formylcarbazole derivative. All these data suggested the compound to be 1-formyl-2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-6-methylcarbazole (12). The neutral product, $C_{19}H_{19}NO_4$

Reagents : i, ozonolysis ; ii, oxidative dealkylation.

(M^+ 325), m.p. 150°, showed ir bands for the presence of NH, straight chain aldehyde and aromatic aldehyde functions, besides the bands for aromatic nucleus. The uv spectral data showed λ_{max} at 228, 235, 244, 297 and 337 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.86, 4.87, 4.72, 4.25 and 3.95), suggesting that one of the formyl (228 nm) group is at 1-position and the alkoxy group at 2-position (235 nm). From all these data the compound has been assigned the structure 13. Acetone obtained from the steam volatile fraction was identified as its 2,4-DNPH derivative, m.p. 128°.

Polonsky⁷, in consideration of previous observations and the results on ozonisation of callophylolide (8), put forward that the ozonisation of 2,2-dimethyl- Δ^8 -pyran system fused to an aromatic residue is abnormal, which involves the migration of the double bond prior to cleavage. From the results of ozonisation of heptazolidine, it appears that the primary product of ozonisation of 2,2-dimethyl- Δ^8 -pyran system fused to an aromatic residue is the tertiary alkoxide with an aldehyde function in the alkoxide residue as in 13, which undergoes oxidative cleavage to yield the hydroxy aldehyde (12) and acetone. This is also supported by the formation of the neutral aldehyde (14) obtained by

Joshi *et al.*¹⁰ from mahamimbine. So the ozonisation is not an abnormal one as was previously assumed. Probably, the isolation of the intermediate tertiary alkoxide with aldehyde function is difficult. With the isolation of the intermediate aldehyde, like 13 during ozonisation, the isolation of acetone by cleavage of the 2,2-dimethyl- Δ^8 -pyran can be rationalised by the oxidation of tertiary alkoxide¹¹ bearing the dimethyl aldehydic residue. From all these data reported above the structure of heptazolidine has been assigned as 2.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The samples were dried over P_2O_5 at 80° before analysis.

Isolation of heptazolidine : The dry powdered roots (1 kg) of *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. and Arn. was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and the residue left after removal of the solvent was chromatographed over silica gel column. Eluates were collected in fractions of 100 ml each. The eluates collected from benzene and petroleum ether mixture yielded a solid which after repeated crystallisation from a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1), furnished heptazolidine, m.p. 150°. It was found homogeneous by tlc in solvent systems, benzene-chloroform (1 : 1), benzene, and benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1) with respective R_f values, 0.74, 0.77 and 0.32 (Found : C, 77.92 ; H, 6.72 ; N, 4.56. $C_{19}H_{19}NO_4$ calcd. C, 77.79 ; H, 6.53 ; N, 4.77%) ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 230, 238, 278, 282 and 335 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.68, 4.86, 4.29, 4.49 and 3.70) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3400, 1650, 1510, 1315, 1380, 1270, 1190, 965 and 985 cm^{-1} .

Dihydroheptazolidine : Heptazolidine (100 mg) in ethanol was shaken with hydrogen in presence of Pd/C (10%, 20 mg) for 10 h when no more uptake of hydrogen was noticed. After the separation of the catalyst and removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed over Brockman's alumina (10 g). Eluates from petroleum ether-benzene mixture furnished an oily mass which yielded crystals, m.p. 130° from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 130° (Found : C, 77.15 ; H, 7.37 ; N, 4.48. $C_{19}H_{21}NO_4$ calcd. C, 77.26 ; H, 7.77 ; N, 4.7%) ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 242, 253, 300, 314 and 328 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.82, 4.68, 4.27, 3.98 and 3.86) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3490, 1590, 1510, 1380, 732 and 780 cm^{-1} .

Ozonolysis of heptazolidine : Ozonised oxygen was passed through a solution of heptazolidine (100 mg) in CCl_4 (25 ml) at 0° until a positive test with starch-iodide paper. The ozonised product was then decomposed under reductive condition heating with 4% acetic acid (100 ml) containing zinc dust for 45 min on a water-bath. The solution was steam distilled and the steam volatile fraction was collected over a solution of 2,4-DNPH while the non-volatile fraction was left in the flask.

(i) 2,4-DNPH of acetone : The yellow DNPH was filtered, dried and dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over alumina (10 g). The eluates

from a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene gave yellow crystals which after crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether gave crystals (homogeneous to tlc), m.p. 127-28°, which did not depress the melting point of a pure specimen of 2,4-DNPH of acetone.

(ii) The non-volatile fraction in the distilling flask was taken up with ether and the ether solution was extracted with 1% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution when phenolic and neutral fractions separated.

Isolation of 12: The residue obtained after acidification of alkaline solution and subsequent work up was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over silica gel (10 g). Eluates from benzene-chloroform (1:1) fraction yielded crystals, m.p. 108-10°. After crystallisation from benzene it melted at 110° (M^+ 255) (Found: N, 5.19. $C_{15}H_{13}NO_3$ calcd. N, 5.49%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 228, 300, 320 and 353 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.64, 4.10, 3.95 and 3.91); ν_{max} (nujol) 3400, 1650, 1600 and 1560 cm^{-1} .

Isolation of 13: The residue obtained from the neutral fraction was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over alumina (10 g). Eluents were collected (25 ml, each). The solid obtained from the benzene eluent after recrystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (1:1) yielded yellow crystals (M^+ 325), m.p. 150° (Found: N, 4.52. $C_{19}H_{15}NO_4$

calcd. N, 4.30%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 228, 235, 244, 297 and 337 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.86, 4.87, 4.72, 4.25 and 3.45); ν_{max} (nujol) 3400, 1740 and 1670 cm^{-1} .

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References

1. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Fortschr. Chem. Org. Naturst.*, 1977, **34**, 299.
2. R. B. SHARMA and R. S. KAPIL, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1980, 158.
3. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, P. BHATTACHARYYA, A. ISLAM and S. ROY, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1974, 808.
4. J. C. BELL, W. BRIDGE and R. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1542.
5. J. C. BELL, R. ROBERTSON and J. S. SUBRAMANIAM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 626.
6. E. SPATH, P. K. BOSE, J. MATZKE and N. C. GUHA, *Chem. Ber.*, 1939, **72**, 81.
7. J. POLONOSKY, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1957, 929.
8. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, B. K. BARMAN and P. K. BOSE, *Sci. Cult.*, 1964, **30**, 445.
9. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, K. C. DAS and P. K. BOSE, *Sci. Cult.*, 1966, **32**, 83.
10. B. S. JOSHI, V. N. KAMAT and D. H. GAWAD, *Tetrahedron*, 1970, **26**, 1475.
11. H. D. ZOOK, J. MARCH and D. F. SMITH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 1617.